

Film Cooling in Supersonic Flow: Experiment Design and CFD Investigation

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Researchers worldwide are thriving to increase the efficiency of gas turbine engines. One possible step increase in overall efficiency could be achieved with the implementation of Rotating Detonation Combustors. However, the development of this technology is held back by several technological challenges. One of the most relevant is presented by the management of the extreme thermal load generated by its unique combustion process. In this context, efficient cooling solutions are crucial. Convection cooling showed applicability limits indicating the necessity of a film cooling approach. A literature review has indicated a lack of experimental results investigating the performance of film cooling strategies in supersonic flow, which extensively characterizes the flow field typical of an RDC. This paper describes the procedure followed for the development of a supersonic wind tunnel capable of investigating the film cooling behaviour in a variable Mach Number flow. Adiabatic effectiveness measurements are planned with the use of Binary PSP, which can account for the temperature gradients appearing on the test article. Global fluid dynamics behavior is then investigated with the implementation of a schlieren imaging set up, capable of capturing the morphology of the mixing mechanisms and shock wave generation at the film cooling hole. Low-order CFD investigations are used to predict the flow behaviour allowing the design of the diagnostic facilities according to the required sensitivity. The outcome of the experimental campaign will provide valuable insight into the physics of these phenomena, promoting the development of a high efficiency cooling solution for the RDC.

Nomenclature

C	=	Concentration
L	=	length
Ma	=	Mach Number
P	=	Pressure
T	=	Temperature
n	=	Refractive index
η	=	Effectiveness
ϵ	=	Deviation

Subscript and Superscript

a	=	adiabatic
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c = coolant
 i = impermeable
 w = wall
 x = relative to the x direction
 y = relative to the y direction
 ∞ = relative to the main flow
 $*$ = relative to the throat / saturation conditions

I. Introduction

The thermal efficiency of gas turbines can be increased with the use of pressure gain types of combustors. Rotating Detonation Combustors (RDC) exploit the fluid dynamic confinement, inherent in a detonative combustion process, to achieve a stagnation pressure gain. A generous amount of papers are available describing the physics of the process and the consequent gain in terms of thermodynamic performance [1][2]. However the application of this technology in gas turbines is still constrained by several technological challenges. One of the most critical is represented by the management of the strong thermal loads associated with the detonative type of combustion process, as described by Rankin et al. [3], St. George et al.[4] and Braun et al.[5] among others.

In this context, researchers have investigated the possibility to mitigate this elevated thermal load implementing film cooling strategies. Promising numerical results have been shown by Yu et al.[6] and by Tian et al.[7]. Furthermore, Sandri et al.[8] showed the limit of purely convective cooling for this type of engine highlighting the need for a film cooled liner solution. Given the extremely high temperature and high power density of a RDC, the investigation of such a system in a reactive test rig, representative of a RDC, is challenging for the moment.

However, a simpler experiment that captures the important physics of the flowfield provides insight into the problem. One of the main characteristic aspects of the flow field in RDC is represented by the periodicity of its outflow and by its supersonic nature. The latter aspect should receive attention if a film cooling strategy is to be implemented, as the Mach number of the main flow plays a role in the definition of the performance of film cooling, as pointed out by Bogard and Thole [9]. The same authors have also provided a thorough description of film cooling, together with the metrics used for its characterization and a survey of the results in the literature[9].

Conventional film cooling in subsonic flow has received extensive attention from the scientific community for many decades and a wide description of its performance is available. For instance, Andreini et al.[10] investigated the adiabatic effectiveness of perforated plates for liner cooling. Furthermore, Schroeder and Thole [11] performed analogous measurements on shaped film cooling holes. However, a performance description of film cooling in supersonic flow is lacking attention from the scientific community. One of the few experimental studies of film cooling in supersonic flow has been done Gritsch et al.[12], who limited the investigation to the characterization of the discharge coefficient. Another relevant work is the one performed by Ligrani et al.[13], who investigated the adiabatic effectiveness of film cooling in supersonic flow up to a Mach number of 1.10/1.12. The measurements have been performed with the use of an infrared camera while the generated shock structure has been captured with the use of a shadowgraphy set up.

For these reasons, the experimental investigation of film cooling with a supersonic Mach number is necessary for the development of a film cooled RDC. In this context, a test rig was developed at the University of Florence to allow the characterization of the performance of film cooling in supersonic flow, CFD simulations have provided support for both the design of the test rig and for the prediction of the experimental results. Based on the computations, dedicated diagnostics approaches required for the investigation of this flow field were developed.

II. Supersonic Flow in RDC

In a RDC the axial flow is typically supersonic. To gain insight into the Mach number characterizing the flow inside an RDC combustor, CFD simulations have been performed. This simulation was conducted using Ansys Fluent utilizing a single step reaction mechanism. The simulation considers a 2D flowfield and solves the laminar NS equations. The considered geometry is representative of the test rig developed at TU Berlin and described in detail by Bach et al.[14]. Fig.1 shows the results relative to the distribution of the Mach number in the RDC, indicating extensive regions characterized by supersonic flow.

For the application of film cooling in a RDC, the analysis is constrained to the region above the detonation wave height, corresponding to the part above the dashed line in Fig.1. This downstream region has been identified by Tian et al.[7] as a viable location for film cooling. This choice is made to prevent hot gas ingestion which is expected to occur

Fig. 1 Mach number distribution in 2D RDC simulation

in the region where the detonation wave progresses. Looking at the Mach number profiles, shown in Fig.2, extracted for different height along the 2D simulated RDC, it is visible that the flow is always partially supersonic. Furthermore, focusing on the profile at the outlet, the flow is almost completely supersonic with small regions of subsonic flow.

Fig. 2 Mach number profiles at different height

While precise indication of the Mach number inside the RDC obtained from CFD simulations were necessary to characterize the extension of the supersonic flow in RDC, there are further evidence indicating the prevalence of a supersonic flow in RDC, especially in the vicinity of its outlet. For instance, Liu et al.[15] investigated the possibility to install a supersonic turbine downstream of the RDC, and for this purpose, a nozzle has been integrated to generate a uniform supersonic flow. The same concept has continued to receive attention recently, with the investigation performed by Su et al.[16] who targeted the same goal but considering three-dimensional simulations of RDC powered by oxygen and hydrogen.

Furthermore, if the RDC is intended to be used in a rocket application, a nozzle is typically aft of the RDC. Therefore, the flow field is characterized even more extensively by a supersonic regime as investigated by Li et al.[17]. The results of their simulation indicate values of Mach number ranging from one to three along the nozzle walls. Nevertheless, even when the RDC technology is considered for gas turbine application, extensive regions of supersonic flow are identified. In this context the experimental investigation of the performance of film cooling in supersonic flow is paramount and represent the main objective of the ongoing experimental activity.

III. Supersonic Wind Tunnel Design

The fundamental component required for this study is a duct capable of delivering a supersonic flow to a film cooled test section. A suction, open loop, wind tunnel has been selected for several reasons. First, the simplicity of its operation: a continuous flow tunnel is easier to control from an experimental point of view. Second, in suction type tunnel the main flow is driven by a pump installed downstream of the test rig and the air is extracted from the room environment acting as the plenum. In this manner two more advantages are obtained: a stable flow readily available guaranteeing stability in the test section, and the ability to operate at pressure levels below atmospheric pressure throughout the wind tunnel ensures safety in the operations. An overview of the layout is shown in Fig. 3. The test rig is composed of four main blocks: the mesh heater, required for the conditioning of the air temperature at the inlet, a plastic intake with low thermal conductivity to avoid the formation of a thermal boundary layer, a center body, and a diffuser. The center body is constituted by a two dimensional convergent divergent nozzle, whose size is indicated in the figure. This convergent geometry geometry allows to reach a Mach number close to 1.4, as validated by the CFD simulations which supported the design. CFD results indicating the distribution of the Mach number in the test rig are shown in Fig.4. The mechanical design allows the replacement of the convergent divergent nozzle, thus allowing variable levels of Mach number to be achieved. Optical access is guaranteed throughout the length of the convergent divergent nozzle and the test section. In addition, an acrylic glass window installed in the top surface, allows optical investigation of the test article.

Fig. 3 Overview of supersonic wind tunnel

A. Test section and Convergent Divergent Design

For this study of film cooling in supersonic flow, a conventional single row of five cylindrical film cooling holes with an angle of 30 degrees has been selected. Furthermore, a transverse pitch of 5D was chosen to avoid interactions spanwise between holes. The size of the holes was selected to be 2 mm which enabled the test section width to be reduced to 5 cm while still enabling side wall boundary layer effects to not impact the film cooling holes. The tunnel height was chosen to be 3 cm to limit the total main mass flow. The wind tunnel is driven by four pumps, which are capable of imposing up to 0.4 kg/s of flow for a pressure difference of 30 kPa.

The design of a convergent divergent nozzle is a common practise already extensively described in the literature. For the convergent part of the duct, no stringent rules have been defined regarding the shape required[18] and in the present study an arc of circumference is considered determining a constriction from the an inlet height of 55mm to a throat height of 25.9 mm. However, for the divergent section more attention is required. The method of characteristics, developed for Matlab by Maurya and freely available[19], has been used for the definition of the divergent section for a Mach number of 1.4 and a test section height of 30 mm, representing the baseline configuration for the test rig. After the definition of the target geometry, CFD simulations have been performed for the computation of the boundary layer thickness, required to correct the baseline geometry accounting for the viscosity effects. This led to the definition of a

Fig. 4 Mach number distribution

throat height of 25.9 m and thus an area ratio between the throat and the test section of $A/A^* = 1.16$.

B. Condensation Issues and thermal considerations

During the expansion leading to supersonic flow the air static temperature decreases drastically and condensation might occur. Several studies have focused on the issue of condensation in supersonic wind tunnels. Early studies performed by Head [20] have shown that the nature of the flow in a supersonic wind tunnel determines a deviation from the quasi-stationary theory of condensation and that a high degree of supersaturation can be expected before condensation actually occurs. Later on, Smolderen[21] in a review of experimental results, compared findings of several authors, and showed that considering different parameters for the indication of the likelihood of condensation, levels of supersaturation not lower than $40^\circ C$ were always identified before the onset of saturation. Condensation is a function of the relationship between the relative and the absolute humidity. The absolute humidity represent the amount of water in a gaseous mixture and it is defined as follows:

$$X_{H_2O} = \frac{n_{H_2O}}{n_{tot}} = \frac{P_{H_2O}}{P_{tot}} \quad (1)$$

where n represent the number of moles, P the pressure, and the subscripts H_2O and tot refer to water and to the mixture considered, respectively. In a given day, with a certain amount of water, this value is fixed, and is independent of heating or cooling on the air stream. The relative humidity Φ is defined as:

$$\Phi = \frac{P_{H_2O}}{P^*_{H_2O}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{H_2O} still represents the partial pressure of water vapour in a given mixture, while $P^*_{H_2O}$ represent the saturation pressure of water, which is a function of the temperature only, according to the August Equation, defined as follows:

$$P^*_{H_2O} [mmHg] = \exp\left(20.386 - \frac{5132}{T}\right) \quad (3)$$

If the partial pressure of water reaches the saturation pressure, the water vapour is at thermodynamic equilibrium and condensation can occur. To investigate the possibility of condensation occurring, four different scenarios representing realistic weather conditions are considered. Namely, air temperature of $19^\circ C$ and $26^\circ C$ are selected and for each temperature two levels of relative humidity are considered: $\Phi = 50\%$ and $\Phi = 80\%$.

Figure 5a shows the state of the partial pressure of water, P_{H_2O} , for increasing Mach number for each of the considered scenarios. While X_{H_2O} remains unchanged during expansion, since P_{tot} decreases, P_{H_2O} must also decrease. In the same plot, the state of the saturation pressure is provided, assuming the expansion starts at the temperatures corresponding to the two scenarios.

At these conditions, it is expected that condensation could be triggered starting at a low subsonic Mach number of around 0.25. To overcome this issue, a heater is installed upstream of the test rig, which could elevate the initial temperature to $110^\circ C$. In this manner the saturation pressure is increased and thus condensation is delayed. Figure 5b shows the state of the partial pressure of water in comparison with the saturation pressure considering a preheating of the air at $110^\circ C$. It is clear, that up to Mach 1.4, the saturation pressure of water $P^*_{H_2O}$ remains above the partial pressure for the four scenarios considered, if the initial temperature is raised, assuring that condensation will not occur.

(a) Partial pressure and saturation pressure evolution from ambient conditions

(b) Partial pressure and saturation pressure considering preheating

Fig. 5 Evolution of water vapour partial pressure and saturation pressure for increasing Mach number

1. Thermal considerations

While preheating represent an optimal solution for the avoidance of condensation phenomena, it obviously has an impact also on the thermal behaviour of the system. As will be indicated later, one of the employed measurement techniques requires the test article to be maintained at a temperature between 0°C and 50°C . During the expansion in a nozzle the temperature decreases dramatically. Nevertheless, this temperature doesn't correspond to the temperature reached by the wall. The temperature of the wall will have a value between the static temperature and the recovery temperature T_r , which corresponds to the temperature that the wall would reach if it was adiabatic and is defined as follows:

$$T_r = T_\infty \left(1 + r \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} Ma^2 \right) \quad r = Pr^{0.33} \quad (4)$$

Figure 6 shows the evolution of the static and the recovery temperature for increasing Mach number starting from a non preheated and a preheated initial condition. It isn't trivial to predict the actual temperature of the wall, however it is known to be between the static and the recovery temperature. To monitor the surface temperature, five thermocouples have been installed in the test plate. From the data shown in Fig.6, it is clear that preheating up to 110°C could determine an excessive wall temperature. For this purpose, during the operations of the wind tunnel, the inlet temperature will be progressively increased, monitoring the temperature of the wall to avoid overheating.

Fig. 6 Evolution of static temperature and recovery temperature for increasing Mach number for different initial conditions

2. Supersaturation

It was shown that by preheating up to 110°C would guarantee the avoidance of condensation. On the other hand, this high temperature could lead to the overheating of the walls. In this context, a compromise can be obtained by relying on the concept of supersaturation of water vapor, i.e. the conditions, outside of equilibrium, in which saturated vapour doesn't show a change of phase. For instance, in Fig.7 preheating is limited to 90°C . In this condition, at Mach 1.4 the saturation pressure would be below the partial pressure for all four considered scenarios. In this context, the level supersaturation can be defined as the difference between the local temperature and the temperature at which saturation would start to occur at equilibrium conditions. For this purpose, the vertical lines in Fig.7a, indicate the Mach number at which condensation would start to occur at equilibrium conditions.

Fig. 7 Definition of supersaturation condition considering preheating

Then, Fig.7b indicates the same vertical line, but in relation to the actual temperature of the flow, during expansion, starting from the considered preheating temperature of 90°C . The temperature difference between the green points and the black point indicates the level of supersaturation, also marked in the figure.

The experimental campaign is relying on the versatility of the heating system, the monitoring of the surface temperature, and the concept of supersaturation to find an optimal compromise that will allow condensation to be avoided while limiting the heating of the test article. The worst predicted condition corresponds to a recovery temperature at Mach 1.4 equal to temperature limit of the test article of 50°C . This conditions is achieved for a preheating limited to 60°C . In this case, a supersaturation above 40°C is identified only in case of a hot and humid day preventing testing. Nevertheless, for the three other weather scenarios considered, supersaturation would remain below 40°C , preventing condensation to occur within the test rig.

IV. Test Rig CFD Simulations

A campaign of CFD simulations has been conducted to predict the performance of film cooling with a supersonic main flow. To obtain a supersonic flow, while limiting the total computational cost, the considered domain corresponds to the convergent divergent section and the test section of the developed wind tunnel. In addition, the domain has been discretized increasing the cell density in the most critical parts, namely the film cooling holes and the test section, as shown in Fig.8. The obtained mesh is composed of 5.8 millions cells. Advancing Layer Mesher has been implemented to allow for a smooth cells distribution at the corners. RANS simulations have been performed selecting the $k - \omega$ model for the turbulence. A turbulence level of 0.5% has been imposed at the inlet.

CFD simulations of the wind tunnel in absence of film cooling have identified a mass flow of 0.2 kg/s and 0.33 kg/s in the test section for the subsonic ($\text{Ma}=0.3$) and supersonic case ($\text{Ma}=1.4$), respectively. To achieve the proper flow rate of coolant, a mass flow inlet boundary condition is chosen for the coolant plenum. It is expected that for the supersonic main flow, at high blowing ratio, the flow in the cooling holes will become choked, requiring higher pressure in the coolant plenum when compared with the corresponding subsonic case. For this study, both the blowing ratio and the Advective Capacity Ratio (ACR) will be computed noting that with the same gas being used for the coolant and the main flow, the effective value of ACR should be nearly identical. However, in the experimental campaign, carbon

Fig. 8 Domain and mesh considered for the CFD simulations with detailed view of injection plate and test section.

dioxide is planned to be the coolant gas which will alter the relationship between blowing ratio and ACR as described by Fischer et al. [22].

Additionally, in compressible flows, the definition of the adiabatic effectiveness is not a trivial choice. According to Fox et al. [23], a good definition for the adiabatic effectiveness, enabling a comparison with experimental data is defined as follows:

$$\eta_{ad}^{r\infty} = \frac{T_{rm} - T_{aw}}{T_{rm} - T_{0c}} \quad (5)$$

where T_{rm} represent the recovery temperature of the main flow, as defined in Equation 4. This expression allows for accounting of the amount of kinetic energy stored within the main flow, but also for the irreversible viscous dissipation occurring within the boundary layer. Yet, this expression does not account for the acceleration of the coolant flow. For lack of a better option, it represents the choice made in other experimental film cooling research and will be used for the present study.

V. CFD Results

This section presents the results of the CFD campaign relative to the six operating conditions considered. Namely, two freestream Mach number have been considered (0.3 and 1.4) and for each freestream condition, three blowing ratio have been selected: 0.3, 0.6 and 1.1. Figure 9 shows the distribution of the calculated adiabatic effectiveness along the centerline of the hole in the streamwise direction. These results indicate that in the near hole region, the lower blowing ratio cools the surface the best, but the coolant is quickly diffused downstream and the adiabatic effectiveness drops. Beyond an $x/D = 4$, the BR=0.6 is the better performing coolant, consistent with the literature. The high blowing condition results in a lifted off jet that performs poorly both near the hole and further downstream. What is interesting is that for each blowing ratio shown, the high Mach freestream results in higher centerline effectiveness values. This is attributed to the high amount of shear being produced by the high velocity crossflow, turning the coolant jet back toward the surface. Furthermore, there is a localized effect of the freestream velocity directly above the coolant hole being

Fig. 9 Adiabatic effectiveness along the centerline of the central cooling hole.

reduced by the presence of an oblique shock at the leading edge of the coolant hole.

Contours of the distribution of Mach number, which better highlights the shock-train formation, is shown together with the computed laterally averaged adiabatic effectiveness (shown as a black line) in Fig.10. The minimum and maximum value of adiabatic effectiveness considered varies in each figure to highlight the impact of the shock formation and its reflection on the adiabatic effectiveness. The contours show the local Mach number distribution. The formation of an oblique shock, created locally due to the injection of coolant, is seen upstream of the coolant hole exit. This shock structure is a three-dimensional phenomena, impacting the distribution of the coolant flow also in the transverse direction. The intensity of the shock formation, and its reflection, increase with increasing values of blowing ratio. This is due to greater mass addition to the main flow, determining a progressively greater obstruction in the path of the supersonic flow. It is also apparent that the reflected shock weakly affects the adiabatic effectiveness. This effect consist on a local interaction of the shock with the coolant film, determining a local separation which locally reduces the adiabatic effectiveness.

Fig. 10 Comparison between the shock train formation shown in terms of Mach number distribution and the laterally averaged adiabatic effectiveness

In addition, the angle of the shock train formation was determined. These results are shown in Figure 11 and indicate an almost linear relation between the BR and the angle generated by the shock. Interestingly, the shock angle, associated with the different levels of blowing ratio is limited, with a range of values between 51.5 and 56.5 degrees. Furthermore, knowing the shock wave angle and the freestream Mach number it is possible to calculate the angle of an equivalent wedge, representing the effects of the injection of the coolant flow on the supersonic main stream. According to Anderson [24], for a given wedge angle, two different oblique shock inclination can be determined: one for the strong shock and one for the weak shock. In the present case, a weak oblique shocks exists. Following the methodology described by Anderson [24], the calculated equivalent wedge angle corresponds to 4.1°, 4.9°, and 6.8° for the increasing values of blowing ratio considered.

Furthermore, the formation of the upstream shock structure generates a local reduction of the velocity of the main supersonic flow. Upstream of the coolant hole the freestream velocity was approximately 425 m/s. Downstream of the shock, this velocity decreases. Since the shock was angled, the velocity also changes in normal direction, so a representative height was chosen at 5 mm above the surface to provide a local freestream velocity. The velocity at this height is shown in Fig.12 from upstream of the hole, through the oblique shock and then past the reflected shock.

Based on this change in freestream velocity, it is informative to introduce the concept of local blowing ratio, adjusting the velocity values of blowing ratio according to the following equation:

$$BR_l = BR \frac{u_m}{u_{ml}} \quad (6)$$

where u_m represents the velocity of the undisturbed main flow five diameters upstream of the injection cooling hole. Subsequently, u_{ml} is the average velocity across the cooling hole exit measured at the center of the cooling hole exit, 5 mm above the injection plane. These calculations show an enhancement of the blowing ratio for the supersonic flow condition. The values of local blowing ratio of 0.31, 0.63, and 1.19 are obtained for the considered blowing ratio of 0.3, 0.6 and 1.1. This enhancement of blowing ratio partially explains the local reduction of the laterally averaged adiabatic effectiveness at the exit of the cooling hole, as the coolant flow penetrates more into the main stream. This effect is more

Fig. 11 Relation between the considered blowing ratio and the corresponding shock train inclination angle.

prevalent at the highest blowing ratios as this also means the momentum flux value is higher and the coolant is more likely to separate.

Fig. 12 Streamwise velocity profile above the central hole 5mm above the injection plate.

VI. Advanced Diagnostics and their Implementation

To investigate the performance of film cooling in supersonic flow, and at the same time understand the physical mechanisms contributing and affecting it, a combination of two experimental approaches are followed. The studies consist on the use of Pressure Sensitive Paints for the measure of the adiabatic effectiveness and the use of schlieren imaging to understand the mixing behaviour and the impact that the expected shock wave generated might have on the the cooling performance.

A. Adiabatic Effectiveness Measurement with PSP

Measurements of adiabatic effectiveness can be directly performed measuring the temperature of a film cooled adiabatic surface. However, in practice, it is impossible to obtain a completely adiabatic surface. For this purpose, it is possible to investigate the performance of film cooling considering an equivalent mass transfer problem instead of a purely thermal problem, with the use of Pressure Sensitive Paint. The implementation of PSP for the measurement of adiabatic effectiveness has been thoroughly described by Jones[25]. Indeed, when the Lewis number of the flow is equal to one, it is possible to implement a heat and mass transfer analogy as described by the following equation:

Fig. 13 Test rig and measurement set up. On the left: schlieren apparatus, on the right: PSP apparatus

$$\eta_{aw} = \frac{T_m - T_{a,w}}{T_m - T_c} = \frac{C_m - C_{i,w}}{C_m} \quad (7)$$

Abdeh and Barigozzi [26] indicated that the use of PSP enables results which are unbiased by the thermal effects associated with the conductivity of the test article. When using PSP, it is then possible to define the adiabatic effectiveness according to the following equation:

$$\eta_{aw} = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\dot{m}_c}{\dot{m}_{air}} \left[\frac{(p_{O_2}/p_{ref})_{air}}{(p_{O_2}/p_{ref})_c} - 1 \right]} \quad (8)$$

However, the validity of this approach is guaranteed only in the case of constant and uniform temperature of the main flow, the coolant flow, and the test article. This occurs since the radiative emission generated by the probe molecules in the paint, returning to the ground state after UV light excitation, is affected by temperature variations of the paint, introducing a source of error in the measurement[27].

In the present test rig, both global temperature variations and local temperature gradients on the test article are to be expected. Firstly, the supersonic flow determines a strong reduction of the static temperature in the main flow, with an impact on the test article temperature. Additional variations might also be introduced by different regulations of power input in the mesh heater or by the duration of the tests, expected to be much shorter than the time required for the rig to reach thermal equilibrium. Furthermore, viscous dissipation and the shock waves generated by the coolant injection could cause local temperature variations, reducing the accuracy of the measurement.

To account for the temperature changes, a binary PSP was implemented into the test rig as shown in Fig.13. Their application has been extensively described by Barigozzi et al.[28]. In the present study, Binary FIB©paint from ISSI are used. This paint, when excited with UV light, emits with different intensities around two different wavelengths. The main emission peak is the one typical of PSP and occurs at $\lambda_{O_2} = 655nm$. This emission is acquired using a long pass filter. However, it also has a temperature dependency. The second emission peak, at a wavelength $\lambda_T = 545nm$, depends only on the surface temperature, independent of the O_2 partial pressure. Thus, using a band-pass lens, it is possible to acquire the intensity of the light around that prescribed wavelength and thus produce a temperature map of the test article. Then, the intensity of the first peak, which depends on both the temperature and the partial pressure of O_2 can have the temperature dependence decoupled from those of the pressure of O_2 thus allowing to obtain reliable adiabatic effectiveness measurements. In the present set up, having only one camera available, the two signals are acquired successively within five seconds of each other. Two filters are contained in a filter wheel, controlled remotely

from a computer, installed downstream of the camera lens as shown in Fig.13. Since the object of the investigation is a steady state phenomena, the lag time between the successive acquisitions does not represent a problem.

B. Shock strength and mixing behavior investigation with schlieren

With the implementation of a schlieren set up, it is possible to capture the density gradients in a flow. The design of the schlieren imaging set up requires the combination of several optical systems, and their selection has an impact on the achievable sensitivity. This technique is based on the variation of refraction index n determined by a variation in density. Indeed, the refraction index is linked to the density according to the relation $n - 1 = k\rho$. Based on this definition, it can be shown that the deviation of the light rays from their straight trajectory can be defined as follows:

$$\epsilon_x = \frac{L}{n_0} \frac{\partial n}{\partial x} \quad \epsilon_y = \frac{L}{n_0} \frac{\partial n}{\partial y} \quad (9)$$

To determine the density gradients, and thus the ray deflection across the whole test section, the previously described CFD results are considered. Since schlieren imaging allows to obtain results which are integrated along the line of sight, it is necessary to integrate Equation 9 along the transverse direction of the test section. From the CFD results, the distribution of the density is available throughout the domain. For the purpose of knowing the total ray deflection it is possible to express Equation 9 in terms of density values, and define its integral along the line of sight, as shown in Fig.14a, leading to the following expression:

$$\epsilon_y = \int_0^{end} \frac{k}{k\rho - 1} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial y} dz \quad (10)$$

where 0 and end represent the boundaries of the domain in the transversal direction. The operations has been applied at different locations where the shock wave was identified, as shown in Fig.14b representing the results of the numerical schlieren and the locations where the integration was performed.

Fig. 14 Visualization of the approach followed for the quantification of the total displacement

The results indicated total deflection angles ranging between one and seven arcseconds. As the total deflection angle in the plume above a low-power reading lamp is around ten arcseconds[29], those results indicate that the possibility of performing schlieren imaging exists, but also that a high sensitivity system is required. Successful results will be enabled by the implementation of a long focal length field lens, allowing the angular displacement determined by the investigated phenomena, to determine a sufficiently large displacement at the focal point. As shown in Fig.13, an axial arrangement with lenses is used due to the limited space in the transverse direction for the implementation of a z-type mirror based set up, following the same approach implemented by Smink et al.[30] for the investigation of an analogous phenomena.

VII. Conclusion

This paper highlights the need to investigate film cooling in supersonic flow, as a fundamental study for the implementation of a successful film cooling strategy for a rotating detonation combustor. In this context, the article

describes the procedure followed for the design of a small scale supersonic wind tunnel. Attention is given to the modelling and prediction of condensation phenomena, representing a critical aspects for the behavior of the wind tunnel. In addition, CFD results representative of the test rig, are presented and analyzed. The results have shown the presence of shock structures forming upstream of the injection cooling holes. Those structures are then reflected on the upper boundary of the tunnel, and then back on the cooled wall. The performed analysis have shown a relation between the prescribed blowing ratio and the orientation of the shock structure. Finally, CFD results indicated the need for high sensitivity and precision Schlieren set up, to capture morphology of these complex flow features. The limitations of conventional measurements approaches for adiabatic effectiveness are presented and suitable diagnostics approaches for the upcoming experimental campaign are described.

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